

PLANNING AND IMPLEMENTATION OF INSTITUTIONAL PROJECT REPOSITORY FOR AIKTC

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ABSTRACT

Many institutions are adopting institutional repositories to gather and preserve their intellectual works. Institutional Project Repositories is developed primarily for assembling, conserving and distributive the scholarly yield of Data. This data assists in sharing and learning of information. For setup of the associate Institutional project Repository and coming up with new strategies with the need of present goal and scope. It becomes difficult to maintain and preserve the final year projects and related documents from the normal system. The primary goal of the Project repository is to preserve the final year project of all the department of AIKTC(Anjuman I Islam Kalsekar Technical Campus). The System handles the documents and the related data of the final year project on the server of the institute. Project repository increases the security of accessible files through updated authentication protocols and storage specifications. With the help of different web technologies & pattern matching algorithm, user can access the project that is done by the previous year students. In this project we are doing the enhancement of the already exist repository of our institute. This System is a web-based application through which our user will upload the project on the server of our institute. These uploaded projects can be accessible to the student of AIKTC.

INTRODUCTION

The advent of the knowledge society and information technologies has significantly added to the event of humanity. However, they need additionally introduced new challenges, at completely different levels, with those involving the digital learning method, that is important to unfold a more and more overwhelming volume of latest knowledge generated. On the one hand, the new age of apprentices (considered as digital natives) and their natural use of latest technologies, addressing data from completely different premises altogether different from those of the past. Then again, academics (digital immigrants), generators of profound changes in society via tutoring and mentoring new competent professionals, but in most cases, restricted in skills in regard to new technologies or their potential uses to extend the potency in education. Institutional Project Repositories is developed primarily for assembling, conserving and distributive the academic yield of Data. This data assists in sharing and learning of information. For setup of the associate Institutional project Repository and coming up with new strategies with the need of present goal and scope. This paper could be a case study of setting up a digital Institutional Repository of comes at Anjuman-I-Islam Kalsekar Technical campus (AIKTC), New Panvel. The essential objective of this Project is to produce a repository to preserve the final year project of various Engineering Departments. The paper conjointly discusses the role of the developer in putting in place a digital Institutional Repository, issues featured and major milestones to hide within the venture. the most objective of this paper is to survey and set up completely different institutional repositories and numerous online offered repositories.

MODULES

A. WEB SERVICE EXPLORE LAYER

This module comprises of the types of services provided by the Institution to the different type of user. The users have also been categorized into different types according to their privileges. This module is subdivided into three categories.

i) Manage: Manage is a service which is given to those users who are registered into the system. The principle goal of the manage service is to upload the project in the repository.

ii) Search: Search access is given to all the users of the institution. User can search the different type of project which are present in the repositories.

iii) Content Filtration: The content which is uploaded by the student of AIKTC is filtered by the Admin.

B. CONTENT MANAGEMENT MODULE

User Registration and Authentication is done in this module. User should register into the system by their college code, branch, Year, Technical Domain, Topic Name, Group Member Name.

User Authentication is done with the help of e-mail verification by sending them to the respected user. Once the user is verified user can upload their project in the repository.

After uploading the Project into the system the compiler will generate the PID (Project ID). This project ID is Unique to different project.

D) GENERATION OF PID

The Above Example shows the generation of the project ID The Id is generate randomly by the system on the basis of the registration.

EXAMPLE OF PID Generation

College Code ----- 1
Branch-----CO
Year-----2017
ID-----01

PID=1CO1701

C. STORAGE SUBSYSTEM

When the user is registered into the system user can upload the project. There are list of protocols which user have to follow while uploading the project into the repository.

List of things User should upload into the repositories.

1. User should upload the complete file/ppt in pdf format.
2. Literature Review of the project.

3. User should upload the synopsis of first phase of project.
4. Technical papers which are referred while planning and implementing of project.
5. Paper Published: Topic and Link of the paper.
6. Other Achievement (if any): Links.
7. Videos (if any).
8. Final Code of the Project.

D. SEARCHING TECHNIQUE

Searching is done on the basis of project is done on the basic of four parameter ie Name of the College, Department of the college, year of the project, Technical domain of the project, Title of the project. If the project is not found on this four parameter the system should give the suggestion of related project to the user.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future this project can be expanded by adding the code authentication module. This module checks the authentication of the project which is been uploaded by the student. This module ensures the institute that the project is genuine and should be uploading on the server Code authentication module consist of the environment to execute the code and check its authenticity. For this we have to create a web application, java, android environment to test the software on this web application.

ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL REPOSITORIES

- **NO PHYSICAL BOUNDARY:** The client of an Institutional repository does not require to go to the library physically; students from everywhere throughout the organization can access a similar data, as long as an Intranet association is accessible.
- **ROUND THE CLOCK AVAILABILITY:** A major advantage of institutional repository is that user can gain access 24/7 to the information of the project.
- **INFORMATION RETRIEVAL:** The client can utilize any inquiry term (branch, year, title, Technical Domain, school) to look through the whole gathering. Institutional archive can give extremely easy to understand interfaces, giving interactive access to its assets.
- **PRESERVATION AND CONSERVATION:** Digitization isn't a long haul conservation answer for physical accumulations, however succeeds in giving access duplicates to materials that would some way or another tumble to corruption from rehashed utilize. Digitized accumulations and conceived advanced articles posture numerous protection and preservation worries that simple materials don't.
- **SPACE:** Institutional Repository can possibly store considerably more data, just in light of the fact that advanced data requires next to no physical space to contain them and media stockpiling advances are more reasonable than any other time in recent memory.
- **ADDED VALUE:** Certain attributes of items, principally the nature of pictures, might be made strides. Digitization can improve decipherability and expel unmistakable imperfections, for example, stains and staining.
- **EASILY ACCESSIBLE.**

CONCLUSION

Moving forward from this paper we will be deciding the best approach to use to implement the Project repository at the AIKTC and how we should import the information from the inheritance database system to Project Hub. Having an understanding of methodologies used when migrating from legacy systems will better enable us to relocate the information efficiently whilst ensuring minimal down time for the legacy system during the migration. Understanding the concepts of metadata and the integral role it plays with the

consistency and accuracy of the content in digital repositories will further enable us to ensure the legacy data migrated to Project Hub is consistent and complete.

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